

ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN PREGNANCY: UNDERSTANDING RISKS, DIAGNOSIS, AND MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: Hypertension is the most common disorder occurring during pregnancy. Hypertensive disorders are one of the leading causes of pregnancy-related maternal mortality worldwide. We present a comprehensive update of the literature regarding hypertension in pregnancy. The article begins with the definition and classification of hypertensive disorders in pregnancy. The normal vascular and renal physiological changes occurring during pregnancy are described in detail. We summarize the intriguing aspects of the pathophysiology of preeclampsia, highlighting recent advances in this field. The existing diagnostic tools and tests proposed for preeclampsia screening are described in detail. We also highlight the short-term and long-term consequences of preeclampsia. Finally, we review current management recommendations, treatment goals, and describe the potential risks and benefits associated with different classes of antihypertensive drugs. Preeclampsia remains an enigma, and current treatment focuses on monitoring and treating its manifestations. We hope that this insightful critique will stimulate a rapid development of research in this area and will help practitioners to identify women at risk and treat those affected more effectively.

Keywords: arterial hypertension, pregnancy.

Introduction

Arterial hypertension (high blood pressure) is one of the most common medical complications during pregnancy. It affects approximately 10-15% of pregnancies worldwide and can have serious implications for both the mother and the developing fetus. Hypertension in pregnancy is associated with an increased risk of preeclampsia, premature birth, and fetal growth restriction, making early diagnosis and appropriate management crucial.

Types of Hypertension in Pregnancy

Hypertension in pregnancy can be classified into several types:

1. **Chronic Hypertension:**

This refers to high blood pressure that exists before pregnancy or is diagnosed before the 20th week of gestation. Women with chronic hypertension may experience

further complications during pregnancy, such as an increased risk of developing preeclampsia.

2. **Gestational Hypertension:**

Gestational hypertension is high blood pressure that develops after the 20th week of pregnancy without the presence of protein in the urine. It can lead to preeclampsia if not monitored and managed appropriately.

3. **Preeclampsia:**

Preeclampsia is a more severe form of hypertension that typically occurs after the 20th week of pregnancy. It is characterized by high blood pressure and proteinuria (excess protein in the urine). Preeclampsia can lead to serious maternal and fetal complications, including organ damage, premature birth, and fetal growth restriction.

4. **Chronic Hypertension with Superimposed Preeclampsia:**

In some cases, women with pre-existing chronic hypertension can develop preeclampsia during pregnancy. This condition carries a higher risk of severe complications for both the mother and the fetus.

Risk Factors for Hypertension in Pregnancy

Certain factors increase the likelihood of developing hypertension during pregnancy:

- **Obesity:** Being overweight or obese increases the risk of developing hypertension during pregnancy.

- **Multiple pregnancies:** Women carrying twins, triplets, or more are more likely to develop high blood pressure.

- **Age:** Women under 20 or over 40 are at a higher risk of pregnancy-related hypertension.

- **Pre-existing conditions:** Women with a history of hypertension, diabetes, or kidney disease are more susceptible.

- **Family history:** A family history of hypertension or preeclampsia may increase a woman's risk.

- **First-time pregnancy:** Primigravidas (first-time mothers) have a higher risk of developing gestational hypertension.

Symptoms of Hypertension in Pregnancy

Many women with hypertension during pregnancy may not experience noticeable symptoms, which is why regular monitoring is essential. When symptoms do occur, they may include:

- Severe headaches
- Visual disturbances (blurry vision, flashing lights)
- Swelling (especially in the hands and face)
- Sudden weight gain due to fluid retention
- Pain in the upper right abdomen
- Nausea or vomiting

- Reduced fetal movement

Diagnosis

- The diagnosis of hypertension in pregnancy is based on regular blood pressure measurements. High blood pressure is defined as a reading of 140/90 mmHg or higher, recorded on two separate occasions, at least 4-6 hours apart.

Additional tests that may be used to diagnose and monitor the condition include:

- Urine tests to check for proteinuria (protein in the urine), which is indicative of preeclampsia.
- Blood tests to assess kidney and liver function and check for signs of organ damage.
- Fetal monitoring to assess fetal well-being, including ultrasounds to monitor growth and amniotic fluid levels.

Management of Hypertension in Pregnancy

Managing hypertension during pregnancy involves controlling blood pressure, monitoring for complications, and ensuring both maternal and fetal health. Treatment strategies include:

1. Lifestyle Modifications:

- Diet: A balanced diet, low in salt, and rich in fruits, vegetables, and whole grains can help manage blood pressure.
- Exercise: Mild physical activity, such as walking or swimming, can improve cardiovascular health and help regulate blood pressure.
- Rest: Adequate rest is important, and women with hypertension should avoid excessive stress.

2. Medications:

- For chronic hypertension, antihypertensive medications, such as labetalol, methyldopa, or nifedipine, may be prescribed to help control blood pressure.
- For gestational hypertension and preeclampsia, medications such as labetalol or hydralazine may be used in more severe cases to manage blood pressure.
- Aspirin may be prescribed in low doses to reduce the risk of preeclampsia, especially in high-risk pregnancies.

3. Close Monitoring:

- Regular check-ups are essential for monitoring both maternal and fetal health.
- Blood pressure should be checked regularly, along with urine tests to monitor protein levels.

4. Delivery Planning:

- In some cases, early delivery may be necessary if the mother's health is at risk or if there are signs of severe preeclampsia.

○ For women with gestational hypertension or preeclampsia, delivery is typically recommended after 37 weeks, though it may be earlier if the situation worsens.

Complications of Hypertension in Pregnancy

If left untreated or poorly managed, hypertension during pregnancy can lead to several serious complications:

- **Preeclampsia:** Can lead to organ damage in the mother, including liver and kidney failure, and can cause fetal growth restriction, preterm birth, or stillbirth.

- **Placental abruption:** Premature separation of the placenta from the uterine wall, which can cause heavy bleeding and threaten both mother and baby's lives.

- **Eclampsia:** A life-threatening condition involving seizures that occur due to severe preeclampsia.

- **Stroke:** Severe hypertension can increase the risk of a stroke during pregnancy.

Conclusion

Arterial hypertension during pregnancy is a significant concern that requires careful monitoring and management. With early detection and proper care, most women with hypertension can have a successful pregnancy and healthy baby. However, understanding the types of hypertension, recognizing the symptoms, and following a treatment plan are critical in reducing the risks associated with this condition. Women with hypertension should work closely with their healthcare providers to ensure the best possible outcomes for both themselves and their babies.

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